

D6.2 First Data Management Plan

Prepared by: UFZ and UOULU

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Author(s)	Christine Liang (UFZ), Élise Lépy (UOULU), Thora Herrmann (UOULU), Ashley Gipson (UOULU)
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Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
ASTD	Arctic Ship Traffic Data
BBNJ	United Nations agreement on biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction
CARE	Collective benefit, authority to control, responsibility, ethics
CBEM	Community-based Environmental Monitoring
CC BY 4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
CMLO	Coastal Marine Litter Observatory
CRM	Certified Reference Materials
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach
DEI	Diverse, Equitable, and Inclusive
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DFG	German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft)
DMP	Data Management Plan
DMS	Dimethyl sulfide
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
Dx.x	Deliverable number
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EMP	Ethics Management Plan
EOM	Earth Observation and Modelling
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union

EU GA	EU Grant Agreement
EU-PolarNet	Integrated European Polar Research Programme
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable
FPIC	Free prior informed consent
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IASSA	International Arctic Social Sciences Association
ICC	Inuit Circumpolar Council
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MS Teams	Microsoft Teams
Mx	Month number
NGO	Non-governmental organization
ODbL	Open Data Commons Open Database License
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PC	Project Coordinator
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PMG	Project Management Group
QA/QC	Quality Assurance/Quality Control
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
RDM	Research data management
RiS	Research in Svalbard
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SIOS	Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System
SSRN	Social Science Research Network

UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNDRIP	United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
WPx	Work package number
.ai	Adobe Illustrator file
.avi	Audio Video Interleave video file
.csv	Comma-separated values
.doc, .docx	Microsoft Word document
.indd	Adobe InDesign document
.jpg, .jpeg	JPEG image file
.mat	MATLAB data file
.mov	QuickTime movie file
.mp3	MP3 audio file
.mp4	MPEG-4 video file
.nc	NetCDF file
.pdf	Portable Document Format
.png	Portable Network Graphics image file
.ppt, .pptx	Microsoft PowerPoint presentation
.pzfx	Prism project file
.shp	Shapefile
.tif	Tagged Image File Format (e.g. GeoTIFF)
.txt	Text file
.xls, .xlsx	Excel spreadsheet

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document is the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) of the ICEBERG project (project number 101135130), which is established by month 6 (M6) of the project. This DMP follows the template recommended for Horizon Europe beneficiaries and addresses the requirements for research data management of Horizon Europe as described in Article 17 (section: Open Science) in the Grant Agreement (EU GA). This deliverable (D6.2) represents the first version of the DMP, which will be followed by the Mid-term Data Management Plan (D6.4) in M18 and the Final Data Management Plan (D6.5) in M36. This deliverable is associated with D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan and D6.3 Ethics Management Plan.

1.2 Purpose

The purpose of the DMP is to describe the data management life cycle of all data sets that will be collected, processed or generated by the ICEBERG project. This plan will cover the entire data management life cycle and will identify the datasets and their descriptions, as well as how the research data will be handled and preserved after the completion of the project. The DMP will adhere to the Open Science Approach and Research Data Management principles. The DMP will also address ethical concerns related to personal data, Indigenous knowledge, biological samples, and artificial intelligence (AI) that arise during the project's life cycle.

1.3 DMP Methodology

The DMP was developed by UFZ in collaboration with UOULU under the Task 6.4 Data management and ethics (UOULU). UFZ and UOULU collected data from all partners regarding data management and ethics (see questions in Appendix 1). The responses have been compiled and are outlined in this plan. The DMP establishes best practices and relevant standards as a quality assurance for the data collected and generated in the ICEBERG project.

2 Data Summary

The ICEBERG data is presented by work packages (WPs), listed below along with the data types that the WPs *mainly* produce or use:

- WP1: in-situ environmental data, model outputs, visual media (e.g. time-lapse images)
- WP2: in-situ environmental data, interviews/focus groups, surveys, visual media (e.g. film, photo voice, drone images)
- WP3: interviews, regulations/legislation information
- WP4: interviews/focus groups, surveys, consortium co-creation data
- WP5: stakeholder information, contact information, visual media (e.g. posters)
- WP6: consortium co-creation data

The DMP defines and establishes consistent practices among project partners in regard to methods within and across work packages. The intention is to increase the efficiency of data handling during the project and increase the quality of research by defining institutional and project-specific data management policies and plans in accordance with relevant standards and community best practice

2.1 WP1: Assessment of pollution sources, distribution, and impacts in Arctic ecosystems

2.1.1 Description

This work package aims to advance the scientific understanding of the sources, distributions, and impacts of pollution across the land-ocean continuum on ecosystem services in the European Arctic. In order to achieve this, the WP will develop model simulations that are complemented by data from remote sensing, as well as in-situ observations and measurements.

The data generated and used by WP1 is summarised in the next section.

2.1.2 Data summary for WP1

Table 1. Data summary for WP1

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
1.6	Quantification of pollution types and amounts (e.g. concentration of PAH, number of microplastic particles) in seawater	Measure different types of pollution, generate data for modelling	.xls, .mat, .txt	Primary data from ICEBERG study sites, Hausgarten (Fram Strait)	5 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, GEOMAR cloud, OSIS (GEOMAR data repository)
1.7	Quantification of changes in biological parameters and biogenic gases in seawater due to presence of pollution (e.g. DMS concentrations, cell counts)	Measure different types of pollution, generate data for modelling	.xls, .mat, .txt	Primary data from ICEBERG study sites, Hausgarten (Fram Strait)	5 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, GEOMAR cloud, OSIS (GEOMAR data repository)
1.3	Quantitative organic pollutant concentrations in sediment, snow and ice	Understand the land-ocean transfer of frozen-lock pollutants and provide a historical perspective on the atmospheric and oceanic sources of pollutants	.xls, .tif	Primary data collected in the field; Secondary data from existing literature	20 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, CNR network drive

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
1.3	Quantitative microplastic concentrations in sediment, snow and zooplankton	Assess the transfer of microplastic in zooplankton	.xls, .tif	Primary data collected in the field; Secondary data from existing literature	20 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, CNR network drive
1.8	Quantitative, qualitative and distributional data on stranded marine litter	Obtain data regarding plastic pollution in the near-shore-open ocean terrestrial environment (the littoral zone) of the Arctic to assess remote sources/anthropogenic and impacts/exchange	.xlsx, .csv	Primary data collected from South-western Sørkappland (Andvika to Breineset), Svalbard; Secondary data generated under Sørkapp Marine Litter Cleanup	20 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, online drive
1.8	Quantitative, qualitative and distributional data on marine litter accumulation rate	Obtain data regarding plastic pollution in the near-shore-open ocean terrestrial environment (the littoral zone)	.xlsx, .csv	Primary data collected in the field from South-western	20 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, online drive

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
		of the Arctic to assess remote sources/anthropogenic and impacts/exchange		Sørkappland (Andvika to Breineset), Svalbard; Secondary data generated under Sørkapp Marine Litter Cleanup			
1.10	Quantitative and qualitative data on chemical composition of freshwater: a) anions, b) cations, c) alkalinity, d) metals (including heavy metals)	Report on impacts of pollution in the European Arctic	.xlsx, .csv, .pdf	Primary data collected in the field from South-western Sørkappland (Andvika to Breineset), Southern Svalbard; area around Longyearbyen, Central Svalbard	20 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, Analytical Chemistry Department of the Adam Mickiewicz University of Poznań network drive (spectrometry analysis data)

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
1.10	Quantitative and qualitative data on chemical composition of soils (including heavy metals)	Report on impacts of pollution in the European Arctic	.xlsx, .csv, .pdf	Primary data collected in the field from South-western Sørkappland (Andvika to Breineset), Southern Svalbard; area around Longyearbyen, Central Svalbard; Secondary data generated by the forScience Foundation in previous years	20 MB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, Analytical Chemistry Department of the Adam Mickiewicz University of Poznań network drive (spectrometry analysis data)

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
1.2	Omics molecular data	Identifying, describing and quantifying the structure, the genetic potential and functional gene expression of the Arctic Ocean Plastisphere Resistome.	.xls, .fastq	Primary data from ICEBERG study sites, Hausgarten (Fram Strait) Generates: Summary table of antibiotic resistance genes and relative abundance.	1000 GB	Open access (deliverables upon completion, raw data upon publication)	Researcher hard drives, GEOMAR cloud, OSIS (GEOMAR data repository), European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)
1.1	Model results with pathways and impact of pollutants in seawater	Identify and trace pollution's potential impacts as well as their temporal and spatial distribution in the European Arctic	.xls, .mat, .txt, .nc	Uses: Primary data from ICEBERG study sites, Hausgarten (Fram Strait); Secondary data from Arctic Ship Traffic Data (ASTD); Generates: Primary data in form of	approx. 2 TB (for subsets of model results)	Open access (prior to publication and/or deliverable report only for ICEBERG consortia members; hereafter, openly accessible)	Researcher hard drives, GEOMAR cloud, OSIS, (GEOMAR data repository)

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
				model results and data – model syntheses			
1.9	Image data collected from tower-based time lapse camera at a pre-defined interval	Continuous monitoring of the litter dynamics through one camera overlooking a single section of a single beach in southern Spitsbergen for a period of one year	.jpg	Primary data directly generated by the time-lapse camera	5 TB	Open access	EOM (Earth Observation and Modeling working group) network drive, CAU Cloud

2.1.3 To whom the data might be useful

The data may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- Researchers writing review papers on Arctic pollution or comparing/tracking changes of Arctic pollution
- Researchers using time series datasets over remote areas (such datasets are rare and usually not available to the research community)
- Communities who rely on the environment for their livelihoods and traditional practices may use this data to understand the potential impacts of pollution on their way of life

2.1.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

The data from WP1 can be used for further publications, proposal applications, and comparison purposes, based on results already published with the agreement of the partners. Data from quantification of pollution, changes in biological parameters due to pollution, and model results may be re-used by partners when writing review papers, inter-comparison studies, and for tracking changes in the future.

2.2 WP2: Risk assessment and local resilience strategies for ecosystems and communities in response to pollution

2.2.1 Description

The aims of this work package are: to assess the impact of pollution and Climate Change on coastal and marine ecosystems and food webs, and their effects on local communities; as well as to provide data that will inform policies and decision-making processes that will help mitigate the impacts of pollution and climate change on coastal and marine ecosystems, food webs, and local communities. In order to achieve this, the WP will analyse changes observed by locals, use satellite and airborne tracking to monitor infrastructure development, co-develop strategies for adaptation with local communities, and establish long-term community-based environmental monitoring systems.

The data generated and used by WP2 is summarised in the next section.

2.2.2 Data summary for WP2

Table 2. Data summary for WP2

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Interview recordings (with community)	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To co-develop strategies for adaptation with local communities	.mp4, .mp3	Primary data collected from communities during interviews in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ ULAP network drives, MS Teams, Dropbox
2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Interview transcripts (with community)	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To co-develop strategies for adaptation with local communities	.doc, .txt, hand-written	Primary data collected from communities during interviews in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk	50 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ ULAP network drives, MS Teams, Dropbox

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Focus group recordings (with community)	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To co-develop strategies for adaptation with local communities	.mp4, .mp3	(Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland) Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ULAP network drives, MS Teams, Dropbox
2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Focus group notes (with community)	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To co-develop strategies for adaptation with local communities	.doc, .txt, hand-written	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	50 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ULAP network drives, MS Teams, Dropbox

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Field notes	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To co-develop strategies for adaptation with local communities	Hand-written, .doc	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, university and institution network drives
2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Survey submissions (text)	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To provide data for the CBEM platform	.xls, .xlsx, .csv	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland); Primary data collected by researchers in Ny-Ålesund (Svalbard) for testing the CBEM platform	50 MB	Open access (except optional contact details)	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives, UFZ/UOULU network drives, LimeSurvey (third party survey host), uMap (third part interactive mapping platform), local curator hard

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
							drive (the community member who quality checks and uploads the data)
2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Survey submissions (images)	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To provide data for the CBEM platform	.png, .jpg	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland); Primary data collected by researchers in Ny-Ålesund (Svalbard) for testing the CBEM platform	5 GB	Open access	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives, UFZ/UOULU network drives, LimeSurvey (third party survey host), uMap (third part interactive mapping platform), local curator hard drive (the community member who quality checks

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Survey submissions (personal data)	To collect optional contact details from survey users if they want to be contacted for more information; To enhance two-way interaction and foster community between citizens and researchers	.xls, .xlsx, .csv	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	20 MB	Not open access	and uploads the data) ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives, UFZ/UOULU network drives, LimeSurvey (third party survey host), uMap (third party interactive mapping platform; servers: OVHcloud), local curator hard drive (the community member who quality checks and uploads the data)

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
2.10	Cartographic data (for CBEM platform)	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To provide data visualisations for the CBEM platform	.shp, .png, .jpg	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	5 GB	Open access	uMap (third party interactive mapping platform), OVHcloud (uMap servers)
2.1, 2.3, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Cartographic data (paper maps)	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To provide an alternative (offline) method for citizens to share geographic data	Paper, .jpg	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	5 GB	Open access (with consent from community members)	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ULAP network drives
2.1, 2.3, 2.7, 2.8	Empathy maps (with community)	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their	Paper and post-its, .jpg	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and	5 GB	Open access (with consent from	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ULAP/UFZ network drives

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
		impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To provide an alternative ethnographic method for citizens to share perceptions		Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)		community members)	
2.1, 2.3, 2.7, 2.8	Photographs from photovoice project	To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To provide an alternative ethnographic method for citizens to share perceptions	.jpg, .png	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	1 TB	Open access (with consent from photographer)	Researcher hard drives, university and institute network drives, personal hard drive of citizen photographer
2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.6, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Photographs and video taken by researchers	To document every phase of the project, especially during fieldwork in Iceland and Greenland	.jpg, .png, .mp4, .mov	Primary data collected from case study sites Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk	1 TB	Open access (unless people can be identified, then consent will be required) by some partners; Not open	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives/devices, university and institute network drives

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
				(Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)		access (internal project use) by some partners	
2.1	Photographs from airborne drone images	To map and monitor marine litter concentrations; To provide images for processing with machine learning algorithms to produce marine litter density maps of study areas	.jpg	Primary data collected by airborne drone mapping from 2-4 coastal sites in Iceland and Greenland	5 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, SCI network drive
2.1.1	Image data collected from tower-based time lapse cameras at a pre-defined interval	For continuous monitoring of the litter dynamics through tower-based cameras overlooking a section of the test beaches	.jpg	Primary data directly generated by the time-lapse cameras	5 TB	Open access	EOM (Earth Observation and Modeling working group) network drive, CAU Cloud
2.1	Marine litter density maps	To map and monitor marine litter concentrations	.pdf	Primary data generated from images collected by airborne drone mapping from 2-4 coastal sites in	50 MB	Open access	Researcher hard drive, SCI network drive, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, Coastal Marine Litter

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
				Iceland and Greenland			Observatory (CMLO) platform
2.2, 2.4	Quantitative data on contamination by various chemical pollutants, i.e. concentrations	Generate analytical data to characterise the occurrence of chemical contaminants in various compartments (environment, food, human), in order to study exposure of the population of Greenland and Iceland to chemical contaminants via their diet	.xls	Primary data generated within the laboratory	1 TB	Open access	Researcher hard drive, ONIRIS network drive
2.2, 2.4	Quantitative datasets from standardized bioassays (e.g. ELISA, RT-PCR, kits for evaluating cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, oxidative stress)	Toxicological assessment of micro- and nano-plastics and other contaminants (PFAS) on human digestive health	.xlsx, .pzfx	Primary data generated within the laboratory	1 TB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, INRAE network drive
	Observation-based data from CMIP6 decadal predictions	To provide climate-related information for the project WPs and for co-development of climate services with Arctic stakeholders	.nc, .csv	Secondary data from public repositories with meteorological station data and model outputs	1 TB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, BSC network drive

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
2.5	Climate-related indicators	To provide climate-related information for the project WPs and for co-development of climate services with Arctic stakeholders	.nc, .csv	Secondary data reusing existing data generated by BSC	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, BSC network drive
2.9	Data on international legal instruments and customary law	To gather information on policy, regulation and legislation covering pollutants in order to provide a synthesis and assessment of existing governance and management approaches; To examine their value for the co-creation of novel/complementary governance approaches under the application of the One Health approach	.pdf	Secondary data reusing publicly available information and data on international legal instruments e.g. (e.g., UNCLOS, BBNJ, UNDRIP, High Seas Treaty, Plastic Pollution Treaty) and customary law	50 MB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams
2.9	Database of regulations	To provide data for WP3 regarding decision-making processes and policies; To identify related legal response measures (e.g. new MPAs) building on international legal instruments and customary law	Online database	Secondary data from legal and policy databases, national and EU databases (EUR-Lex), UN treaty database	50 MB	Open access	Researcher hard drive, WaveLinks database

2.2.3 To whom the data might be useful

The data may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- Researchers, for example in social science and humanities working on Arctic pollution or governance
- Researchers working on marine and coastal dynamics can access marine litter density maps on the Coastal Marine Litter Observatory (CMLO) platform and use them to improve the detection and mapping of marine litter in the coastal zone
- Interested community members who want a visualisation of pollution and to monitor their local environments long-term (CBEM data)
- Public health authorities may use the data to improve health related strategies
- Management authorities, municipalities and conservation authorities at the local level can use the data to inform land use planning, climate change adaptation and mitigation plans, and for pollution control
- Management authorities and decision makers for EU Arctic policy can use the database of regulations to allow for easy compilation and review of regulations applicable to different pollutants within each jurisdiction.
- Educators using drone/time-lapse image datasets for teaching beach and litter dynamics

2.2.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

Data generated by WP2 may be used as a case study for future publications or research outputs. Quantitative data (e.g. pollutants, plastics, contaminants) may be re-used for comparison purposes for future studies. Interview data from community members will be re-used only if prior consent for this is established. These data can be used for comparison studies in the future of long-term interviews series, and with other Arctic projects and sites. The database of regulations allows for easy re-use of data through compilations and reviews of regulations applicable to different pollutants within each jurisdiction. This would facilitate future Arctic pollution governance research as well as research on global frameworks. Media (photos, videos, paper maps, photovoice entries) may be re-used as visual aids for non-commercial, pedagogical and scientific purposes. Further, the videos may be re-used for film screenings, schools, and conferences (for non-commercial purposes). Drone images will be re-used to retrain machine learning algorithms for detecting marine litter in the Arctic environment. In addition, since collection of drone and time-lapse camera image data and upkeep of the time lapse cameras and the drones involve local communities/schools in Iceland and Greenland, this data may also be re-used for teaching purposes by the partners or the communities.

2.3 WP3: Facilitating effective science-based pollution-control governance

2.3.1 Description

This work package aims to support and strengthen the implementation of the EU Arctic policy, 3rd Arctic Science Ministerial meeting and the work of the Arctic Council in regards to the effective prevention and mitigation of pollution in the Arctic. In order to achieve this, the WP will examine the existing governance approaches and their challenges and shortcomings for providing specifically tailored novel policy recommendations. Data generated by this work package will contribute to an understanding of the science-policy nexus (WP1) and strengthen the application of a truly holistic approach (WP2).

The data generated and used by WP3 is summarised in the next section.

2.3.2 Data summary for WP3

Table 3. Data summary for WP3

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
3.1, 3.2, 3.3	Interview recordings (with national and international policy-makers)	To provide data for WP3 regarding decision-making processes and policies	.mp3	Primary data collected during interviews with decision-makers and experts at a supra-local level (not community members) in Iceland, Greenland, and Norway (regarding Svalbard)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, ULAP network drives, Dropbox
3.1, 3.2, 3.3	Interview transcripts (with national and international policy-makers)	To provide data for WP3 regarding decision-making processes and policies	.doc	Primary data collected during interviews with decision-makers and experts at a supra-local level (not community members) in Iceland, Greenland, and Norway (regarding Svalbard)	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, ULAP network drives, Dropbox
3.1.5	Interview recordings (with case study region political stakeholders)	To gather insights on the local perspectives (national and subnational political level) of existing governance gaps with regard to pollution control	.m4a	Primary data collected during interviews with political actors, authorities and further societal stakeholders in Iceland and Greenland	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, CAU cloud

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
3.1.5	Interview transcripts (with case study region political stakeholders)	To gather insights on the local perspectives (national and subnational political level) of existing governance gaps with regard to pollution control	.doc	Primary data collected during interviews with political actors, authorities and further societal stakeholders in Iceland and Greenland	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, CAU cloud
3.4	Interview recordings (with case study region women's associations)	To gather insights for the analysis and identification of gaps and opportunities for the integration of a gender-dimension of different forms of pollution in the case study regions	.mp3, .mp4, .mov, .avi	Primary data collected during interviews with community members of women's associations in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland); Qaqortoq, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Greenland)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams
3.4	Interview transcripts (with case study region women's associations)	To gather insights for the analysis and identification of gaps and opportunities for the integration of a gender-dimension of different forms of pollution in the case study regions	.doc, .xlsx, .pdf	Primary data collected during interviews with community members of women's associations in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland); Qaqortoq, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Greenland)	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
3.6	Recordings and minutes from policy lab meetings (recommendation/building) with decision-makers and community members	To elaborate final recommendations, their formulation and evaluation.	.mp3 .docx	Primary data collected during policy labs (meeting minutes).	1 TB	Not open access	MS Teams and OneDrive
3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.1.5, 3,4	Data on local, national, regional and international marine pollutants governance	To gather information on policy, regulation and legislation covering pollutants in order to provide a synthesis and assessment of existing governance and management approaches; To examine their value for the co-creation of novel/complementary governance approaches under the application of the One Health approach	.pdf	Secondary data reusing publicly available information on local, national, regional and international data on Marine pollutants governance	20 MB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams

2.3.3 To whom the data might be useful

The data may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- Researchers in Arctic governance would be interested in the novel data from political stakeholders
- Management authorities and decision makers for EU Arctic policy
- Crucial actors (e.g. environmental organizations and NGOs) working on pollution prevention and mitigation in the Arctic

2.3.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

Data generated by WP3 may be re-used for further publications and future governance comparison research. Interview data from will be re-used only if prior consent for this is established. Interview data from decision-makers can be used to compare insights from Greenland, Iceland and Svalbard with future insights obtained from decision-makers in other Arctic regions, focusing on environmental governance, management and the One Health approach. Data on regulations will be included in the regulatory and policy database, as well as in the public background papers published by project month 15. These would be designed to be part of cross-project integration and reuse by other researchers.

2.4 WP4: Co-Creation, Ethics, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion

2.4.1 Description

This work package develops: an overarching framework that ensures research adherence to co-creation, ethics, diversity, equity, and inclusion in all WPs; as well as a Diverse, Equitable, and Inclusive (DEI) research code of conduct and ethical standards for co-creation, data management, and knowledge dissemination. In order to achieve this, the WP supports the co-production and coordination of methodologies across WPs, provides all WPs with recommendations on co-creation, develops guidelines for engaging with Indigenous partners and amplifies existing protocols for community-based research. This WP also co-creates monitoring and evaluation criteria for the project in collaboration with local communities.

The data generated and used by WP4 is summarised in the next section.

2.4.2 Data summary for WP4

Table 4. Data summary for WP4

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
4.1	Consortium Stakeholder Analysis notes	To identify stakeholders the project intends to involve in co-production processes	Online (Miro Board), .jpg	Primary data generated during internal online workshops with consortium members	N/A	Open access (screenshots in public level reports)	Miro Board
4.1	Consortium Flow of Information Timeline notes	To identify points of interdependencies and collaboration in terms of data collection and co-production	Online (Miro Board), .jpg	Primary data generated during internal online workshops with consortium members	N/A	Open access (screenshots in public level reports)	Miro Board
4.2	Consortium reading group notes	To generate insights for the ICEBERG project based on consortium co-creation in ethics; To provide a shared space across disciplines and WPs to reflect on project ethics	Online (Miro Board)	Primary data generated during internal online reading group meetings with consortium members	N/A	Not open access	Miro Board
4.5	Empathy maps (with consortium)	To provide initial feedback about the CBEM platform from a user's perspective ahead of public release	.pptx, .jpg	Primary data generated during internal online	50 MB	Open access (screenshots	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams,

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
		and community consultation meetings		workshop with consortium members		in public level reports)	researcher hard drive, UFZ network drive
4.2, 4.4	Interview recordings (with community)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with communities	.mp4, .mp3	Primary data collected from communities during interviews in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive
4.2, 4.4	Interview transcripts (with community)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with communities	.doc	Primary data collected from communities during interviews in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	50 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
4.2	Interview recordings (with consortium)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with consortium	.mp4, .mp3	Primary data collected from online and in-person meetings with consortium members	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive
4.2	Interview transcripts (with consortium)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with consortium	.doc	Primary data collected from online and in-person meetings with consortium members	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive
4.2	Focus group recordings (with community)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with communities	.mp4, .mp3	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsarsuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
4.2	Focus group notes (with community)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with communities	.doc, hand-written	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsarsuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive
4.2	Focus group recordings (with consortium)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with consortium	.mp4, .mp3	Primary data collected from online and in-person meetings with consortium members	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive
4.2	Focus group notes (with consortium)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with consortium	.doc, hand-written, online (Miro Board)	Primary data collected from online and in-person meetings with consortium members	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive, Miro Board

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5,	Field notes	To co-create strategies with local communities in the dimensions of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), gender, and ethics	Hand-written, .doc	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsarsuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	50 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, university and institution network drives
4.2, 4.4, 4.5,	Photographs and video taken by researchers	To document every phase of the project, especially during fieldwork in Iceland and Greenland	.jpg, .mp4, .mov	Primary data collected from case study sites Akureyri and Husavik (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsarsuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives/devices, university and institute network drives
4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4,	Survey submissions (from consortium)	To co-create strategies and guidelines with the consortium in the dimensions of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), gender, and ethics	.xls, .xlsx, .csv, online	Primary data collected from consortium members using various online survey platforms	20 MB	Not open access	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives, university

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
							or institute network drives, Mentimeter (third party presentation-based digital tool), Webropol (third party survey platform)

2.4.3 To whom the data might be useful

The data may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- Other projects generating guidelines in the dimensions of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), gender, and ethics
- Researchers and projects working closely with local communities e.g. co-creating strategies and frameworks
- Researchers and projects looking for alternative ethnographic methods of co-creation and reflection

2.4.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

Much of the data in WP4 is generated internally and intended to be used as insights when co-creating guidelines and frameworks relating to the project. Thus, the data may be continuously re-used throughout the project life cycle to update “living documents” (e.g. ICEBERG Code of Conduct). Interview data collected from communities may be used in future comparison studies with other projects/sites, which will be explicitly explained in consent forms.

2.5 WP5: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach

2.5.1 Description

This work package is responsible for handling the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation of results to maximize project outreach and facilitate dialogue with relevant stakeholders (e.g. Indigenous communities, local communities, civil society organizations, policy and decision makers, financial institutions, and environmental managers). In order to achieve this, the WP: uses a co-design approach in designing inclusive science communication activities together with the project partners and stakeholders; promotes the project and progress with targeted communication activities to relevant stakeholders and wider society; and increases exchange of information between the project and its stakeholders.

The data generated and used by WP5 is summarised in the next section.

2.5.2 Data summary for WP5

Table 5. Data summary for WP5

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
5.1	Stakeholder database for email lists	To communicate the progress and outcomes of the project via newsletters	.xls	Primary data collected from the ICEBERG website newsletter sign-up form	20 MB	Not open access	Project directory in Mailchimp
5.2	Stakeholder database for events	To communicate the progress and outcomes of the project through events	.xls	Primary data collected from the ICEBERG website newsletter sign-up form and consortium members' contact lists	20 MB	Not open access	Kaskas's Google Workspace
5.3	Media database	To communicate the progress and outcomes of the project to the media and through press releases	.xls	Primary data collected from consortium members' organisations; Secondary data from media websites and	20 MB	Not open access	Kaskas's Google Workspace

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
5.4	Visual media (posters)	To promote the project with targeted communication	.pdf, .jpg, .ai, .indd	Meltwater Media Monitoring Primary data generated from project information	20 GB	Open access	Kaskas's Google Workspace, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams

2.5.3 To whom the data might be useful

The stakeholder data contains personal information and will not be reused by other researchers or third parties. Posters conveying ICEBERG project information may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- Other projects and researchers conducting research in the Arctic region who want to connect and collaborate
- Local communities who are interested in the activities of the ICEBERG project and want to participate
- Educators in the field using posters for pedagogical purposes to showcase recent research developments

2.5.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

The stakeholder data contains personal information and will not be reused by project partners following completion of the project. Stakeholder and media contact details will only be stored until the end of the project. ICEBERG visual media such as posters may be re-used by project partners in the future, for example to showcase their participation in a successful project or demonstrate their expertise.

2.6 WP6: Project Coordination and Management

2.6.1 Description

This work package is in charge of ensuring the efficient management of work, coordination and the timely production of high-quality outcomes, as well as submitting reports to the European Commission. In order to achieve this, WP6 coordinates work between partners and WPs and manages the data generated by the project (which includes producing the DMP).

The data generated and used by WP6 is summarised in the next section.

2.6.2 Data summary for WP6

Table 6. Data summary for WP6

Task(s)	Type of data	Purpose	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
6.2	Official documents	Quality Assurance Plan (D6.1)	.txt, .pdf, .doc	Secondary data from EU GA and CA	3 MB	Open access	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams Official location of the EU GA?
6.4	Database created for DMP and EMP	First Data Management Plan (D6.2) Mid-term Data Management Plan (D6.4) Final Data Management Plan (D6.5) Ethics Management Plan (D6.3)	.xls, .txt, .pdf, .doc	Primary data collected from ICEBERG project consortium beneficiaries	3 MB	Open access (resulting management plans)	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams

2.6.3 To whom the data might be useful

The data may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- EC project officers and review boards who are checking that the management of quality, data, and ethics in the project are compliant with standards
- Other projects and researchers conducting similar research who want to learn more about project coordination data
- Stakeholders (e.g. community, decision makers, media) who want to understand the steps being taken to ensure the quality of the project and be reassured that the project will meet their expectations

2.6.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

The data management plans are an iterative process and data will be re-used, as well as added to throughout the project lifecycle. As the data contributes to the management of quality, data, and ethics in the project, key insights on best practice may be re-used and applied to other projects if applicable.

3 FAIR data

As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), the DMP outlines below the management of data based on FAIR principles. For data from each WP in ICEBERG (as summarised in Section 2), this section will describe how the data is:

- **Findable:** others can find your data, for example in a repository, with metadata and a persistent identifier.
- **Accessible:** others can access your dataset as long as there are no issues, for example privacy issues.
- **Interoperable:** others and machines can open the files, for example with open file formats, and can combine this dataset with other datasets, for example through metadata standards.
- **Reusable:** the above three principles, plus others can understand the data and know how they can reuse it, for example if the data is documented and licensed.

3.1 Criteria for FAIR data

Table 7. Questions asked to determine how the data complies with each FAIR category (Horizon EU DMP Template, 2021)

Findable	Accessible	Interoperable	Reusable
<p>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</p> <p>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery?</p> <p>What metadata will be created if metadata standards do not exist in your discipline?</p> <p>What disciplinary or general standards will be followed?</p> <p>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</p> <p>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</p>	<p>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository and be assigned an identifier (e.g. DOI)?</p> <p>Will all data be made openly available (including adopting open data formats)?</p> <p>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?</p> <p>If access to (open) data is restricted, how is the access controlled?</p> <p>How long will the data remain available and findable?</p> <p>Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain license?</p> <p>Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</p> <p>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included?</p> <p>Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?</p>	<p>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will be followed to make the data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?</p> <p>Will community-endorsed interoperability best practices be followed?</p> <p>In case it is unavoidable that project specific ontologies or vocabularies are generated, will these be openly published to allow reusing, refining or extending them?</p> <p>Will the data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from the project, or datasets from previous research)?</p>	<p>How will documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use be provided (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</p> <p>Will the data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?</p> <p>Will the data be licensed using standard reuse licenses?</p> <p>Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</p> <p>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</p> <p>Will data quality assurance processes be applied to the data?</p>

3.2 WP1 Data

3.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All WP1 data is open access (Table 1) and will be made available in public repositories that provide the data with a persistent identifier to make the data findable. The public repositories are listed in the next section (Section 3.2.2). Standard persistent identifiers issued by these repositories are DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) and URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers). The public repositories provide a search field that supports simple keyword style searches as well as advanced searches (e.g. with Boolean operators). Search keywords supplied during data upload to repositories optimise the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

Metadata standards for WP1 data are listed in Section 3.2.3. Rich metadata (additional information or details that are included with the data) include descriptions, file type, date created, and other relevant information that helps provide context and improve searchability, discovery, and visibility. WP1 data will be accompanied by metadata that is required by each specific repository. As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin), in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords. Metadata will be created in a way that allows easy harvesting and indexing by using established metadata standards (e.g. set by the public repository) and ensuring it is associated with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), to promote compatibility with indexing tools and systems.

3.2.2 Making data accessible

All WP1 data (11 data types) are open access (Table 1). WP1 data will be made accessible through the following public repositories:

- PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science
- Zenodo open repository
- OceanRep GEOMAR repository
- SIOS Data Management System (for Svalbard data)
- Open repositories of specific journals (to be decided when generating publications)

PANGAEA and Zenodo assign DOIs to data as persistent identifiers, while OceanRep assigns URIs. The SIOS Data Management System assigns a unique ID to each dataset.

WP1 data is accessible for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International". All data types in WP1 include an open data file format, allowing the data to be accessed by means of a free standard protocol. The data will remain available and findable via the public repositories after the project's end (and will be uploaded not later than two years after the completion of the ICEBERG project). Furthermore, model data will be included as open source code in GitHub.

3.2.3 Making data interoperable

In order to make the data interoperable, WP1 applies the following metadata and methodological standards:

- ISO 19115: Metadata standard for describing geographic information and services
- IPTC: Photo Metadata standard
- ISO 17025: General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories
- ISO/IEC 10918: Guidelines for digital compression and coding of continuous-tone still images

To promote data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines, common and established methodologies for the field will be followed, and where possible adhere to the current scientific

literature. For example, distributional data on stranded marine litter follows the protocol developed for the Sørkapp Marine Litter Cleanup project (forScience, 2021) and the Deep Dive Protocol (Falk-Andersson, 2021).

3.2.4 Increase data re-use

WP1 permits re-use of data under license CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International", in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement. The data is made freely available in the public domain via online repositories and will remain accessible to third parties after the end of the project. Documentation in the form of read-me files, xls/csv sheets, and supplementary material in publications containing information on methodology and other relevant information (e.g. variable definitions, units of measurements, etc.) will be provided to facilitate data re-use.

The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP1 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Outlier detection to identify and remove anomalies or errors in datasets
- Regular maintenance, calibration, and checking of equipment
- Checking for errors in sample handling and data entry (human error)
- Field team training and supervision
- Digital scale calibrated for usage in exact location
- Laboratory tests apply double sample analysis, calibration procedure and Certified Reference Materials (CRM) for control

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

3.3 WP2 Data

3.3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Not all data from WP2 is open access (Table 2) due to sensitive and personal data (see Section 6.2 Data Protection). However, open access data will be made available in public repositories that provide the data with a persistent identifier to make the data findable. The public repositories are listed in the next section (Section 3.3.2). Standard persistent identifiers issued by these repositories are DOIs. The public repositories provide a search field that supports simple keyword style searches as well as advanced searches (e.g. with Boolean operators). Search keywords supplied during data upload to repositories optimise the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

Metadata standards for WP2 data are listed in Section 3.3.3. Rich metadata (additional information or details that are included with the data) include descriptions, file type, date created, and other relevant information that helps provide context and improve searchability, discovery, and visibility. Open access WP2 data that is uploaded to repositories will be accompanied by metadata that is required by each specific repository. As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin), in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords. Metadata will be created in a way that allows easy harvesting and indexing by using established metadata standards (e.g. set by the public repository) and ensuring it is associated with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), to promote compatibility with indexing tools and systems.

3.3.2 Making data accessible

Of the 21 data types generated by WP2, 13 data types are open access (Table 2). This is due to methods such as interviews and focus groups generating sensitive data that could identify participants (see Section 6.2 Data Protection). Of the open access data types, there are still some caveats and restrictions to making the data public. For example, survey data collecting pollution observations for the CBEM platform are displayed on the open access uMap interactive mapping tool. However, users may opt to provide contact information if they wish to be contacted by the researchers. This constitutes sensitive and personal data and will not be displayed on the CBEM platform. Many of the community activities data outputs (paper maps, empathy maps, photovoice entries) are expected to be open access but need to have consent from the community first.

WP2 open access data (note: not all data) will be made accessible through the following public repositories:

- SocArXiv open archive of the social sciences
- Zenodo open repository
- SSRN Social Science Research Network repository
- Data INRAE – The INRAE data repository
- Open platform for French public data (www.data.gouv.fr)
- Coastal Marine Litter Observatory (CMLO) online web platform
- Open repositories of specific journals (to be decided when generating publications)

SocArXiv, Zenodo, SSRN, Data INRAE, and the Open platform for French public data assign DOIs to data as persistent identifiers. Marine Litter Density Map Reports can be viewed through the CMLO platform, which assigns a unique ID to each data (can be accessed by clicking on the data points).

WP2 open access data types are accessible for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0 (with the exception of the CBEM survey data). However, it is noted that WaveLinks (used for the WP2 database of regulations) is a living database under constant development and the CC BY 4.0 license may change in future. Open access survey data for the CBEM is made accessible on the uMap platform, which uses the license Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL). The open access data types in WP2 include an open data file format (with the exception of map data), allowing the data to be accessed by means of a free standard protocol. However, digital cartographic data such as the CBEM pollution observations and the litter density maps are uploaded onto platforms that allow public accessibility. CBEM data is loaded onto uMap and litter density data is loaded on the the CMLO online web platform, which makes viewing map data free and accessible. The data will remain available and findable via the public repositories after the project's end (and will be uploaded not later than two years after the completion of the ICEBERG project).

Although data types that are not open access (raw data such as interview transcripts) cannot be published due to data protection guidelines and regulation, these data may still generate open access outputs. For example, aggregated insights will be published in open access journal articles. Anonymised or aggregated data containing no personal data may be uploaded to public repositories. Only the project partners and individuals listed in the consent form are able to access the raw data. Restricted access of data is ensured by storage on password protected researcher/network drives, or on project shared drives (ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams) that are password and two-factor authentication protected.

3.3.3 Making data interoperable

In order to make open access data interoperable, WP2 applies the following metadata and methodological standards:

- DCMI - Dublin Core Metadata Standard

- EXIF metadata standards for native images
- ZonMW metadata standards for health research
- OSPAR Commission metadata standards for map data
- uMap/OpenStreetMap metadata standards
- WaveLinks database metadata standards
- Bibliographical standards for legislative and policy document
- ISO 17025: General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories
- ISO 9001: Creating, implementing, and maintaining a Quality Management System
- ISO17043: General requirements for the competence of proficiency testing providers
- INFOGEST 2.0 standardized protocol for food digestion simulation

To promote data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines, common and established methodologies for the field will be followed, and where possible adhere to the current scientific literature. For example, drone images will be collected using the SciDrones Marine Litter Data acquisition protocol (SciDrones PC Spinoff, n.d.). Contaminant samples analysed to study exposure will follow official laboratory methods from the French National Reference Laboratory (LABERCA). Field data collection follows standard social science protocols for interviews, focus groups, and surveys, including standard consent and information form templates. Personal information follows anonymisation protocols, for example using the tool QualiAnon (Nicolai et al., 2021).

3.3.4 Increase data re-use

WP2 permits re-use of open access data under licenses CC BY 4.0 and ODbL. The data is made freely available in the public domain via online repositories or open access platforms and will remain accessible to third parties after the end of the project. Documentation in the form of read-me files, xls/csv sheets, and supplementary material in publications containing information on methodology and other relevant information (e.g. appendices for consent form and information sheets) will be provided to facilitate data re-use. Data from WaveLinks and uMap are also downloadable as csv files, which allows users to extract and re-use the information in their own analyses.

The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP2 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Lab methods that are ISO 17025 accredited so QA/QC are included to monitor analytical performances
- Lab sample processing uses experimental replicates
- Statistical analyses of lab results using the software GraphPad Prism 9.1 to detect anomalies or outliers
- Climate data (CMIP6 decadal predictions and climate indicators) are post-processed using software to run diagnostic skills assessments
- Cross-checking transcripts for key interviews
- Intercoder evaluation for transcripts
- Checking for errors in data entry and handling (e.g. assuring that transferring data from one storage location to another one will not affect the data)
- Community participant training on SciDrones Marine Litter Data acquisition protocol for optimizing drone flight preparation.
- Automated pre-processing of collected drone images to ensure data integrity and reducing faults or corrupted data
- Training/capacity building for uMap to familiarise users with capabilities and functions

- Guideline/manuals for citizens and curators to use uMap
- Quality check by local curators for CBEM platform data
- Data entry protocols in CBEM survey that reduce entry error
- Training of citizens for maintenance of time-lapse cameras and how to conduct regular quality checks
- Regular quality checks by citizens for functionality of equipment, quality of data, and assessment of data captured (e.g. is the data suitable for future methods?)
- Quality check by WaveLinks database managers

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

3.4 WP3 Data

3.4.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Part of the data generated in WP3 is not open access (Table 3) since much data generated in WP3 is interview data, which includes potentially sensitive insights and personal information (see Section 6.2 Data Protection). However, these data will generate open access outputs (e.g. aggregated insights, anonymised data, database), which will be published in open access journal articles or uploaded to public repositories that assign persistent identifiers such as DOIs. Data on local, national, regional and international marine pollutants governance is the only data type in this WP to be open access. This data will be made available on Zenodo, which assign DOIs. A database of regulations and policies will constitute another open-access dataset. These repositories provide a search field that supports simple keyword style searches as well as advanced searches (e.g. with Boolean operators). Search keywords supplied during data upload to repositories optimise the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

Metadata standards for WP3 data are listed in Section 3.4.3. The WP2 marine pollutants governance data that is uploaded to repositories will be accompanied by metadata that is required by each specific repository. As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin), in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords. Metadata will be created in a way that allows easy harvesting and indexing by using established metadata standards (e.g. set by the public repository) and ensuring it is associated with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), to promote compatibility with indexing tools and systems.

3.4.2 Making data accessible

Of the 21 data types generated by WP3, only 1 data type is open access (Table 3). This is due to the main data type (interviews) generating sensitive data that could identify participants (see Section 6.2 Data Protection). Although raw data such as interview transcripts cannot be published due to data protection guidelines and regulation, these data may still generate open access outputs. For example, aggregated insights will be published in open access journal articles. Anonymised or aggregated data containing no personal data may be uploaded to public repositories.

Interviews with political stakeholders may be open access if interviewees consent and the transcripts are partly anonymised. Only the project partners and individuals listed in the consent form are able to access the raw data. Restricted access of data is ensured by storage on password protected researcher/network drives, or on project shared drives (ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams) that are password and two-factor authentication protected.

WP2 open access data (marine pollutants governance data and aggregated insights from interviews) will be made accessible through the following public repositories:

- SocArXiv open archive of the social sciences
- Zenodo open repository
- SSRN Social Science Research Network repository
- Aggregated insights from interviews will be submitted in publications to open access journals (to be decided when generating publications)

SocArXiv, Zenodo, SSRN, and open access journals assign DOIs to data as persistent identifiers. WP3 open access data types are accessible for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International". The data will remain available and findable via the public repositories after the project's end (and will be uploaded not later than two years after the completion of the ICEBERG project).

3.4.3 Making data interoperable

In order to make open access marine pollutants governance data interoperable, WP3 will apply bibliographic standards for legislative and policy documents. To promote data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines, common and established methodologies for the field will be followed. Field data collection follows standard social science protocols for interviews and focus groups, including standard consent and information form templates. Personal information follows anonymisation protocols, for example using the tool QualiAnon (Nicolai et al., 2021).

3.4.4 Increase data re-use

WP3 permits re-use of open access data (marine pollutants governance data and aggregated insights from interviews) under license CC BY 4.0. The data is made freely available in the public domain via online repositories and will remain accessible to third parties after the end of the project. Supplementary material in publications containing information on methodology and other relevant information (e.g. appendices for consent form and information sheets) will be provided to facilitate data re-use.

The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP3 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Cross-checking transcripts for key interviews
- Intercoder evaluation for transcripts
- Checking for errors in data entry and handling (e.g. assuring that transferring data from one storage location to another one will not affect the data)

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

3.5 WP4 Data

3.5.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Most of the data generated by WP4 is not open access (Table 4) due to sensitive and personal data (see Section 6.2 Data Protection). Technically, no raw data generated by WP4 is open access, however, some

consortium co-creation data will be screenshotted from their original media (PowerPoint, MiroBoard, Mentimeter) and presented in public level reports. Thus, this section will refer to the provisions made for FAIR management of the reports that feature WP4 open access data. Public level reports will be made available in repositories that provide the data with a DOI persistent identifier to make the data findable. The public repositories provide a search field that supports simple keyword style searches as well as advanced searches (e.g. with Boolean operators). Search keywords supplied during data upload to repositories optimise the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

Metadata standards for WP4 data are listed in Section 3.5.3. Rich metadata (additional information or details that are included with the data) include descriptions, file type, date created, and other relevant information that helps provide context and improve searchability, discovery, and visibility. Open access WP4 data that is uploaded to repositories will be accompanied by metadata that is required by each specific repository. As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin), in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords. Metadata will be created in a way that allows easy harvesting and indexing by using established metadata standards (e.g. set by the public repository) and ensuring it is associated with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), to promote compatibility with indexing tools and systems.

3.5.2 Making data accessible

Of the 15 data types generated by WP4, 3 data types are open access (Table 4). These data are derived from consortium co-creation workshops and shared via public level reports. The other data types are not open access due to methods such as interviews and focus groups generating sensitive data that could identify participants (see Section 6.2 Data Protection). However, these data may still generate open access outputs (e.g. aggregated insights, anonymised data), which will be published in open access journal articles or uploaded to public repositories that assign persistent identifiers such as DOIs. Only the project partners and individuals listed in the consent form are able to access the raw data. Restricted access of data is ensured by storage on password protected researcher/network drives, or on project shared drives (ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams) that are password and two-factor authentication protected.

WP4 open access data (consortium co-creation data and aggregated interview/focus group insights) will be made accessible through the following public repositories:

- SocArXiv open archive of the social sciences
- Zenodo open repository
- SSRN Social Science Research Network repository
- Aggregated insights from interviews will be submitted in publications to open access journals (to be decided when generating publications)

SocArXiv, Zenodo, SSRN, and open access journals assign DOIs to data as persistent identifiers. WP4 open access data types are accessible for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International". The data will remain available and findable via the public repositories after the project's end (and will be uploaded not later than two years after the completion of the ICEBERG project).

3.5.3 Making data interoperable

To promote interoperability within and across disciplines, common and established methodologies for the field will be followed. Field data collection follows standard social science protocols for interviews and focus groups, including standard consent and information form templates. Personal information follows anonymisation protocols, for example using the tool QualiAnon (Nicolai et al., 2021).

3.5.4 Increase data re-use

WP4 permits re-use of open access data (consortium co-creation data and aggregated interview/focus group insights) under license CC BY 4.0. The data is made freely available in the public domain via online repositories and will remain accessible to third parties after the end of the project. Supplementary material in publications containing information on methodology and other relevant information (e.g. appendices for consent form and information sheets) will be provided to facilitate data re-use.

The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP4 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Cross-checking transcripts for key interviews
- Intercoder evaluation for transcripts
- Checking for errors in data entry and handling (e.g. assuring that transferring data from one storage location to another one will not affect the data)

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

3.6 WP5 Data

3.6.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Most data from WP5 is not open access (Table 5) since the majority of data generated in this WP represent stakeholder contact details, which includes personal information (see Section 6.2 Data Protection). Visual media with research data (e.g. scientific posters) is the only data type in this WP to be made open access. This data is not typically uploaded to repositories; however, it may be made available on the ICEBERG website or conference websites and proceedings. For example, if a poster was submitted to the EGU (European Geosciences Union) Assembly, metadata including the abstract (describes purpose, methods, key findings), authors, and date of presentation would be associated with the poster. This abstract would be uploaded to the Copernicus Publications repository and assigned a DOI. This repository provides a search field, which would promote the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin) in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords if uploaded to a repository/conference website.

3.6.2 Making data accessible

Of the 4 data types generated by WP5, only 1 data type is open access (Table 5). These data are derived from available project information and shared via visual media (e.g. posters). The other data types are not open access due to the inclusion of personal data (see Section 6.2 Data Protection). Restricted access of data is ensured by storage on password protected researcher and company drives, or on project shared drives (ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams) that are password and two-factor authentication protected.

WP5 visual media are made publicly accessible through the ICEBERG website, social media pages, and press releases. Depending on the purpose and target audience, the visual media may be included on conference websites and proceedings, which may be associated with a DOI. The posters are accessible

for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0. The data will remain available and findable after the project's end as long as the website will remain functional.

3.6.3 Making data interoperable

The visual media data is made interoperable through standardised file formats for the graphic design discipline. In order for project partners and third parties to view and use posters, these are converted to an easy to access machine-readable format such as pdf or jpg. Visual media are subjected to a check for cross-platform support, ensuring that content can be displayed and accessed on a wide range of devices, including computers, smartphones, and print media.

3.6.4 Increase data re-use

WP5 permits re-use of open access data (promotional visual media e.g. posters) under license CC BY 4.0. The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP5 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Using file version control to track changes and updates made to visual media content
- Quality check for cross-platform support to ensure that visual media content can be displayed and accessed on a wide range of devices (e.g. smartphone vs. computer) and for print media
- Establishing project guidelines (e.g. ICEBERG Communication Guidelines) to monitor and regulate the use of visual media content
- Establishing feedback mechanisms to gather feedback from partners on the usability and effectiveness of visual media, and use this input to continually improve and enhance them

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

3.7 WP6 Data

3.7.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All data generated by WP6 is open access (Table 6). Deliverables are all public level reports that will be made available in repositories that provide a DOI persistent identifier to make the data findable. The public repositories provide a search field that supports simple keyword style searches as well as advanced searches (e.g. with Boolean operators). Search keywords supplied during data upload to repositories optimise the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

Deliverables that are uploaded to repositories will be accompanied by metadata that is required by each specific repository. As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin), in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords. Metadata will be created in a way that allows easy harvesting and indexing by using established metadata standards (e.g. set by the public repository) and ensuring it is associated with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), to promote compatibility with indexing tools and systems.

3.7.2 Making data accessible

The data from WP6 will be shared via public level reports and uploaded to Zenodo. Since Zenodo is an open research data repository that is hosted and managed by CERN and funded by the European Commission, it would be appropriate to upload project deliverables to this repository. This multidisciplinary repository accepts multiple data types, publications, and software and assigns a Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

WP6 data are accessible for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International". The data will remain available and findable via the public repositories after the project's end. In addition, once approved by the European Commission, the deliverables will be available on our website. Data from WP6 will be uploaded in a timely manner as the deliverables follow a predetermined schedule with fixed deadlines.

3.7.3 Making data interoperable

The project has created a QAP (D6.1) that states naming conventions for files. A template for deliverables created by WP5 also includes a descriptive metadata page.

3.7.4 Increase data re-use

WP6 permits re-use of open access data (public deliverables) under license CC BY 4.0. The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP6 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Using file version control to track changes and updates made to deliverables
- Establishing feedback mechanisms to gather feedback from partners on all deliverables as a quality check

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

4 Other research outputs

4.1 Research outputs besides data

Other research outputs for the ICEBERG project are:

- Models
- Policy briefs
- User guides
- White papers
- Databases
- Toolboxes
- Online citizen participation platform
- Website, blogs, and social media pages

4.2 FAIR management of research outputs

The considerations pertaining to FAIR data are applied to non-data outputs, for example use of metadata standards and uploading of outputs to open repositories. The following are examples of how the ICEBERG project plans to manage and share research outputs based on FAIR data principles:

- As per the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1), the partners must – as soon as possible (but not before a decision on their possible protection) – disseminate results, for example, through online channels (website/social media platforms), peer-reviewed publications (open access), or conference presentations
- As per the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1), the partners must follow standards for bibliographic metadata of open access research outputs (see Section 4.3)
- Deliverables (policy briefs, user guides, white papers, databased, toolboxes) are public level dissemination and will be uploaded to ICEBERG website, open repositories and assigned a DOI
- Outputs uploaded to open repositories will follow the repository's metadata standards, providing as much detail as possible using standardised vocabularies used in the corresponding discipline
- Quality assurance in calibre of deliverables through version history tracking and reviews by the project management team and consortium partners (and also in some cases, the project ethics advisor and advisory board)
- Deliverables provide provenance metadata (version history and authors) and descriptive metadata (e.g. work package number, dissemination level), using the template created by UOULU and KASKAS
- Online citizen participation platform is hosted by open access interactive mapping tool uMap, which is free and open source
- Model code for the assessment of impacts of pollutants in seawater will be made available on GitHub following the repository's metadata standards
- Use dissemination channels such as the website, blog posts, and social media pages to increase discovery of outputs and promote re-use by interested third parties
- Dissemination measures should be consistent with the 'DECO strategy' (D5.2), following guidelines to increase impact and re-use by interested third parties

- All partners will contribute to dissemination activities to promoting collaboration and knowledge-sharing within the project research disciplines and across disciplines (thereby promoting re-use of information)

4.3 Open access to research outputs

As per the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1), each partner must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

Partners must:

- As soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications
- Aim to deposit at the same time as above, the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications
- Ensure open access to the deposited publication via the repository at the latest on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities)
- Ensure open access to the deposited publication via the repository to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the deposited publication

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- The terms "European Union (EU)" and "Horizon Europe"
- The name of the action, acronym and grant number
- The publication date and length of embargo period if applicable
- A persistent identifier

5 Allocation of resources

5.1 Costs for FAIR data and research

The costs for making data and research outputs FAIR are costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, and security. Indirect costs (e.g. entire RDM teams at institutes) would be associated with higher expenses, but they would not need to be covered by the project budget. The resources associated with these costs are listed below.

Potential direct costs for making the data FAIR in the ICEBERG project are:

- Time used by partners for data curation, documentation, and providing rich metadata
- Time used by partners for uploading of metadata and datasets to open repositories
- Opportunity costs of time spent by partners on data management instead of other project tasks
- Open access costs paid to journals for publication of articles that are publicly accessible
- Costs for resources required for data storage and backup (e.g. Miro Board costs)
- Costs for maintaining data infrastructure and systems for long-term data accessibility (e.g. yearly website fees)
- Costs for hiring external expertise in data management (e.g. ICEBERG Ethics Advisor for consulting on ethics of data sharing and security)

Potential indirect costs for making the data FAIR in the ICEBERG project are:

- Costs for resources required for institution data storage and backup (e.g. institute network drives)
- Costs for personnel at partner institutions to advise in research data management (e.g. data protection officers, RDM units)

Partner effort (measured in person-months or PMs) is covered by project funding and would include time used by partners to enact FAIR data protocols. As per the EU GA, the activities related to the DMP (such as providing guidance on data management and open access issues and preparing the DMP) will cost about 0.5 PM for the whole duration of the project. Open access publication costs and compensation mechanisms for external expertise are also included in the project budget.

The project-wide storage locations for data include various cloud storage servers (e.g. OneDrive, Dropbox) and online tools (e.g. MS TEAMS). The associated costs for storage in network drives are incurred by the partner institutes, with the main project storage costs (ICEBERG OneDrive/MS Teams) covered by the UOULU IT infrastructure. The cost for the ICEBERG Miro Board has been incurred by project partner WoA. Long term accessibility of the website will be maintained and funded by KASKAS. Costs for hiring RDM personnel are incurred by the partner institutes.

5.2 Data management responsibilities

All individuals in the project have some responsibility for data management. The below table outlines the key roles and responsibilities for data management (Table 8).

Table 8. Roles and responsibilities for data management in the ICEBERG project

Role	Responsibilities
<p>Data provider/researcher</p>	<p>Describe the data using appropriate Metadata or discipline standards</p> <p>Apply quality assurance protocols when generating or processing data (and post-processing)</p> <p>Deposit open access data in open repositories or publish scientific publications in open access journals</p> <p>Participate in dissemination activities (e.g. conferences, writing blog posts for the ICEBERG website) to promote sharing of data, with the support of the project DECO team</p>
<p>WP leads</p>	<p>Provide input to the data management plan and check accuracy of expected data types</p> <p>Implement data management protocols from the ICEBERG DMP in their respective WPs (including FAIR principles)</p> <p>Contacting the project management team and ethics advisor in case of ethical and privacy issues with data</p> <p>Participate in dissemination activities (e.g. conferences, writing blog posts for the ICEBERG website) to promote sharing of data, with the support of the project DECO team</p>
<p>Project coordination team (WP6)</p>	<p>Monitor data management activities and deadlines and send reminders to partners</p> <p>Offer support and further guidance for filling out the data surveys</p> <p>Monitor that open results are deposited in public repositories</p> <p>Participate in dissemination activities (e.g. conferences, writing blog posts for the ICEBERG website) to promote sharing of data, with the support of the project DECO team</p>
<p>Data management team (T6.4 leads)</p>	<p>Develop the data management plans throughout the project lifecycle in cooperation with the project partners</p>

Role	Responsibilities
DECO team	<p>Request and compile information about data generated or used by partners</p> <p>Ask partners for missing information or clarifications</p> <p>Provide support and provide solutions for specific issues about project data management</p> <p>Promote communication and sharing of data to broad and general audiences</p> <p>Support partners in communicating and sharing data</p> <p>Provide platforms (e.g. social media, blog) for partners to share data</p> <p>Organise events to disseminate data and outputs</p>
Ethics advisor	<p>Advise on the ethical dimensions of data management, for example data protection and security</p> <p>Support the writing of the data management plans</p> <p>Support the project management and data management teams in providing guidance to WP leads and partners around data protection</p> <p>Work with partners and project management team to resolve critical issues around data ethics</p>

Furthermore, the DESCA ICEBERG Consortium Agreement Attachment 6 also defines the following roles concerning processing of personal data:

- Data controller: the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the Processing of Personal Data, where the purposes and means of such Processing are determined by the European Union or Member State law, as per Article 4(7) GDPR
- Data processor: a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes Personal Data on behalf of a Data Controller, as per Article 4(8) GDPR.

As per these definitions, the project will have many data controllers and processors. Typically, the data controllers will be the partner institutes, and are listed with their legal names, for example Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH (trade name: UFZ). Who the data processors are will depend on the methods used to collect or generate data. For example, if using a survey method, the data processor would be the third-party survey platform (e.g. LimeSurvey GmbH). For interview methodology, the data processors may be the partner institutes themselves (unless a third-party service is used, for example a professional transcription service).

Of the 16 consortium partner institutions, all have data protection officers except six who do not have a dedicated role for data protection. However, these institutions have a responsible person for data management who may deal in the aspects of data protection.

6 Data security

6.1 Provisions for data security

Data (with the exception of personal data) is stored at a minimum for 5 years according to the EU GA (record-keeping for 5 years after final payment; pg. 13, Point 6), but preferably for 10 years according to good scientific practice (DFG, 2019). Personal data is deleted after anonymisation or after project completion at the latest. Open access data will be deposited and stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation.

The following provisions are in place for data security, which includes data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data:

- Implementing data backup and recovery procedures to prevent data loss (e.g. backing up files in the ICEBERG OneDrive, making shared folders for WPs)
- Implementing access controls and authentication mechanisms to ensure that only authorized individuals can access sensitive data (e.g. multifactor authentication to access the ICEBERG OneDrive)
- Where possible, implementing secure file transfer protocols such as SFTP (Secure File Transfer Protocol) or HTTPS (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure) when transferring sensitive data between researchers (e.g. using ICEBERG OneDrive to share data, which uses HTTPS to encrypt data transferred between researcher drives to OneDrive servers)
- Implementing data anonymisation for interviews and focus group data to reduce the risk of personal data exposure
- Explicitly specifying in consent forms who has access and rights to raw data

In addition, project partners with their own institutional policies for handling and secure storage of sensitive data will be required to adhere to these protocols. The policies and protocols can be found here:

- University of Oulu Research Data Management Guide (<https://libguides.oulu.fi/researchdata>)
- University of Lapland Principles (<https://www.ulapland.fi/EN/About-us/Our-principles/Data-protection>)
- University of Kiel Data Management Plan (<https://www.datamanagement.uni-kiel.de/de/ressourcen/dokumente/cau-dmp-recommendations-pdf>)
- UFZ Guidelines on Research Data Management (<https://rdm.pages.ufz.de/guidelines/>)
- GEOMAR Research Data Policy (https://doi.org/10.3289/data_policy_V1_2022)
- SAI uses: Personal Data Protection Policy of the University of Akureyri (<https://www.unak.is/english/university/strategies-and-policies/personal-data-protection-policy-of-the-university-of-akureyri>)
- INRAE Personal Data Protection Policy (https://www.inrae.fr/sites/default/files/pdf/PolitiqueProtectionDonnees_INRAE-Uk_0.pdf)
- AIRCentre Personal Data Protection Guide (https://www.aircentre.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Personal_Data_Protection_Guide.pdf)
- Barcelona Supercomputing Center Policy (<https://www.bsc.es/res-intranet/legal-notice>)

6.2 Data protection regulations

This section will present the regulations for data protection that are relevant to the case studies. See Section 7.3 Personal Data for instances and groups that these regulations apply to.

6.2.1 GDPR

Greenland, Iceland, and Svalbard are all subject to the GDPR, or Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation). Listed below is a summary of three GDPR articles relating to processing of personal data that are particularly relevant for the ICEBERG project.

Article 5 of the GDPR states that processing of personal data must comply with *all* six principles:

- Lawfulness, fairness and transparency: data is processed fairly, lawfully and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject
- Purpose limitation: data is collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not processed in a manner incompatible with those purposes
- Data minimization: data is adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary to the purpose for which they are processed
- Accuracy: data is accurate and up to date, with steps taken to ensure inaccurate personal data are erased or rectified without delay
- Storage limitation: data which permits identification of data subjects are kept for no longer than what is necessary to the purpose for which they are processed
- Integrity and confidentiality: data is processed in a secure manner

Article 6 of the GDPR states that processing of personal data must satisfy *at least one* of the following conditions:

- Data processing is carried out with the data subject's consent
- Data processing is necessary for the performance of a contract with the data subject;
- Data processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation
- Data processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject
- Data processing is necessary for the public interest or in the exercise of official authority
- Data processing is necessary for the legitimate interests of the data controller, except where overridden by the interests of the data subject

The ICEBERG project will always complete the first condition – that is informed consent must be obtained from the data subject (see Section 7.2). As per Article 7 of the GDPR, the conditions for consent for data processing are:

- The data controller must be able to demonstrate that the data subject has consented to processing of their personal data
- The request for consent must be presented in a manner which is clearly distinguishable from the other matters in the consent form, in an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language
- The data subject has the right to withdraw their consent at any time (in an easy way) and are informed of this prior to giving consent
- When determining if consent is freely given, consider if the performance of a contract is conditional on consent to the processing of personal data that is not necessary for the performance of that contract (in other words, consent should not be coerced or required for something unrelated to the purpose of the research)

6.2.2 Country specific regulations

In addition, there are several country specific legislations that cover processing personal data, formalities to obtain consent to process personal data, and special rules when processing personal data about children and vulnerable groups. The relevant regulations of the case study countries are:

- Greenland: Danish Personal Data Act in effect from the 25th of May 2018
- Iceland: Act on the Protection of Privacy in regards to the Processing of Personal Data, No. 77/2000
- Svalbard: Norwegian Law on the Processing of Personal Data (Personal Data Act) in effect from the 15th of June 2018

The relevant regulations of the consortium partner countries are (note: only those collecting personal data are listed):

- Finnish Data Protection Act (1050/2018)
- German Federal Data Protection Act of 30 June 2017
- Spanish Organic Law 3/2018 of December 5 on Protection of Personal Data and Guarantee of Digital Rights

6.3 Third parties

Some data in the ICEBERG project is handled by third parties. In the event that the third party is used to process data, a data processing agreement according to Article 28 GDPR (Processor) is in place. The below table presents the third parties used, their purpose, and their data protection agreement.

Table 9. Third parties who handle data from the ICEBERG project

Third party	Purpose	Data protection agreement
Miro Board	Digital whiteboard platform used to generate and display data co-created by the consortium	https://miro.com/legal/vendor-data-processing-addendum/
Webropol	Survey tool used to collect data from consortium members	https://webropol.co.uk/privacy-policy/
Mentimeter	Survey tool used to collect data from consortium members	https://www.mentimeter.com/dpa-statement
LimeSurvey	Survey tool used to collect data on pollution observations from citizens for the CBEM platform	https://www.limesurvey.org/privacy-notice
uMap	Used as the CBEM platform to display pollution observations data	https://umap.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/2022.03.23-Private-Information-Protection-Policy.pdf

Third party	Purpose	Data protection agreement
Mailchimp	Used to collect and store stakeholder email lists for ICEBERG newsletter	https://mailchimp.com/en/about/security/
Microsoft OneDrive and Teams	Data storage	https://www.microsoft.com/licensing/docs/view/Microsoft-Products-and-Services-Data-Protection-Addendum-DPA
Dropbox	Data storage	https://www.dropbox.com/privacy
Google Cloud Storage	Data storage	https://cloud.google.com/terms/data-processing-addendum

7 Ethics

ICEBERG will establish an Ethics Management Plan (D6.3) to define ethical principles, develop an ethics evaluation framework, and ensure compliance with EU/national legal and ethical requirements in the countries where the project's activities are carried out. This section of the DMP will only focus on the ethics of data sharing. More information can be found in the ICEBERG Ethics Management Plan. In addition, the ICEBERG Code of Conduct (D4.2) is a framework for self-regulation that includes practices for internal and external research collaboration framed through the concepts of fairness, respect, care, and honesty.

7.1 Ethics of data sharing

The following are ethics and legal issues that could have an impact on data sharing in the ICEBERG project:

- The project involves research with local communities and Indigenous Peoples (adults, youth, elders). The project must consider how to share data with local communities and Indigenous communities, and how to ensure that the data benefits them. See Sections 7.4 Vulnerable groups and 8.1 Indigenous and traditional knowledge.
- Participant selection among participating communities must take into consideration inclusiveness and an aim for diverse representation regarding both gender, identity, social-cultural and socio-economic factors. However, participant selection is limited to those that can give informed consent.
- In case of the possibility for unexpected findings, they would be handled according to the normal procedures at each organisation, referring participants beforehand to the relevant support services. In the case of Greenland, ethical procedures will be elaborated and take into account the ongoing process in Greenland to establish ethical guidelines for research with Greenlandic communities.

As per the ICEBERG Description of the Action (DoA) Section 4 Ethics Self-Assessment, possible ethical issues will be minimised by:

- Developing ethical principles that will be implemented in the research process (D6.3 EMP)
- Only collecting data that is necessary for the research context
- No personal data is to be transferred between partners in different countries

7.2 Informed consent

Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation will be included with methodologies dealing with personal data. All study participants will be asked for their written informed consent for taking part in the study and for data processing before the start of the interview, focus group, or survey.

Voluntariness and informed consent will be ensured by:

- Plain language written consent forms and participant information sheets will be provided, as well as oral explanations of the purpose and format of obtaining data
- Clear explanation on all parts of the consent form prior to any interview or stakeholder engagement, with opportunities for data subject to ask questions
- The researcher will provide honest and thorough answers for any questions asked about the consent form or research

- Check for understanding throughout the consent process to ensure that the individual fully comprehends the information and is making an informed decision
- Ensure that the individual understands that they can withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or repercussions
- The researcher will document the consent process by keeping detailed records of all discussions, questions asked, and the individual's consent (in field notebooks)
- Consent form outlines how data will be processed, stored, used, and potentially re-used. It will also include the contact details of the project coordinators.

More information about the consent process as well as consent forms that will be used for the ICEBERG project will be available in D6.3 Ethics Management Plan. In addition, Article 7 of the GDPR presents the conditions for consent for personal data processing (see Section 6.2). To summarise: the researcher must be able to show that participants have consented to processing of their personal data, consent for personal data processing must be presented in a manner which is clearly distinguishable from the other matters in the consent form, and the participant must be informed prior to giving consent of their right to withdraw at any time.

7.3 Personal data

As per the ICEBERG DoA Section 4 Ethics Self-Assessment, personal data will be treated according to personal data processing legislation – The General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 and local personal data protection regulations in EU and non-EU/EEA partner countries (see Section 6.2). See Section 6.2 for relevant data protection regulations followed by the ICEBERG project. No personal data is to be transferred between partners in different countries. All persons involved in a task jointly create this personal data (for each of their respective countries) - data is not transferred between countries but it is accessible for all the owners as it is considered that all their respective countries are original locations of the data. Only anonymised or aggregated data will be shared with partners. Personal research data will be destroyed after the end of the research project.

The DESCA ICEBERG Consortium Agreement Attachment 6 defines the roles of data controller and data processor (see Section 5.2). As per these definitions, the data controllers will typically be the partner institutes, while the data processors will depend on the methods used to collect or generate data. ICEBERG partner institutes are the data controllers bound by data control laws and regulations while those bound by data processing laws and regulations can be both ICEBERG partners and third parties if/when third parties somehow use or process the ICEBERG data. For example, if using a survey method, the data processor would be the third-party survey platform (e.g. LimeSurvey GmbH). For interview methodology, the data processors may be the partner institutes themselves (unless a third-party service is used, for example a professional transcription service). In the case that a third party is used to process data, a data processing agreement according to Article 28 GDPR (Processor) is in place. To summarise: ICEBERG decides what data is collected, makes anonymous, stores, shares, and destroys the data while third parties do not. ICEBERG also processes, gathers, and analyses the data and third parties may also do this when it is allowed.

Personal data processed in the ICEBERG project are:

- Data collected in Informed Consent form (names and email addresses)
- Signed consent forms
- Optional contact details collected from CBEM platform survey (e.g. names and emails, telephone numbers)
- Gender, date of birth and/or age (the participants will not include minors)
- Job description/domain of activity (e.g. for interviews with stakeholders and political actors)
- Area of living (region/city/area code)

- Photographs and video materials (e.g. from art-based methods)

Sensitive data are personal data consisting of racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, genetic data, biometric data, data concerning health or data concerning sexual orientation. This kind of data can only be processed if a condition for processing special category data is satisfied, but these data are not relevant in the ICEBERG Project. In the case of, for example, interviews where sensitive data is shared, whatever sensitive information the participants choose to share is up to them and as willing study participants they do it voluntarily and with informed consent of the study. ICEBERG does not specifically ask questions about sensitive information.

7.4 Vulnerable groups

The ICEBERG project works with Inuit communities in Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland. Since participant selection among participating communities will take into consideration inclusiveness and aim for diverse representation, there is also a possibility that other vulnerable group members will take part in the research. For example: people with disabilities, people facing socio-economic challenges, the elderly, and pregnant women. The project will not involve persons under 16 years of age. The table below presents potential risks to vulnerable groups and mitigation strategies to minimise these risks.

Table 10. Potential risks to vulnerable groups and how to mitigate them.

Potential risk	Mitigation strategy
Recalling traumatic events in relation to climate change triggered by some of the questions	Right to withdraw at any time. Interviews will be carried out with the presence of an elder that has the trust of the community and can intervene with culturally appropriate ways
Worry of findings disrupting traditional way of life or producing negative results about their community	Co-creation methodologies, research transparency of project goals, and open discourse about findings
Worry that participants will be used for time and contributions without adequate compensation	Mechanisms in place for compensation of research participants
Misrepresentation of information expressed in interviews through analysis of researcher	Presenting/sharing research findings with interviewees prior to publication, and giving them the opportunity to input, suggest or amend before publication. Co-analysis of empirical material and community-review process.

The project also aims to ensure data sharing with local and Indigenous communities, and to ensure that data benefit them. Below are the strategies that will be employed by the project:

- Regular workshops and meetings with community members for feedback and to share findings
- Printed transcript of their own interviews will be sent
- Photographs and interviews will be electronically sent to the local coordinator

- Communities' wishes, needs and preferences will be discussed during the community consultation meeting (what research questions are relevant to different community members)
- Local representatives in project advisory board and feedback meetings with advisory members throughout project process
- Local pollution mitigation strategies co-produced and shared with communities
- Co-production of knowledge and close stakeholder engagement
- ICEBERG will employ local co-researchers and seek to involve locals also as co-authors of publications
- A call for local student/early-career-researchers will be made in partnership with local institutions, for example KNAPK, or Ilisimatusarfik (University of Greenland), and SAI. Ethical considerations around data storage, such as privacy aspects will be addressed in detail in the EMP (D6.2).
- Co-define appropriate ways for sharing the data (e.g. presentation by another partner that works onsite), which will be generated following a co-production approach
- Co-creation of a CBEM platform: Communities' wishes, needs and preferences will be discussed during the community consultation meetings. Photographs and data go through a local curator. Ethical considerations around data storage, such as privacy aspects will be addressed in detail in the EMP (D6.2).
- Care is taken to communicate in the language of the case study regions through translation of materials and hiring local translators
- Regular review of potential risks of data sharing throughout the project timeline
- Through an iterative process, each step of the research will be validated by the communities and the community steering group (WP4)

7.5 Ethical governance procedures

Of the 16 consortium partners, six institutions have an ethics committee. In addition, two institutions are in the process of setting up an ethics committee and one institution has an internal research board. Some institutions also have legal departments and data protection officers that ensure compliance with personal data protection. None of the partners are required to go through ethics clearance or approval as part of the ICEBERG project.

The following ethical governance procedures will be followed:

- CAU Kiel Guidelines for good scientific practice
- DFG Guide to Good Scientific Practice
- European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
- Ethics for researchers- Facilitating Research Excellence in FP7
- Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK guidelines 2019)
- French Office for Research Integrity (Ofis) guidelines
- High Council for Evaluation of Research and Higher Education (Hcéres) guidelines
- Nagoya Protocol
- Rules for Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice at the UFZ
- Svalbard Environmental Protection Act
- University of Aegean ethical regulations (followed by SCI as a spinoff company)
- University of Akureyri Code of Ethics

8 Other issues

8.1 Indigenous and traditional knowledge

It is important to be aware that data in the project generated as a result of working with Indigenous communities may be subject to different or additional considerations. Science in modern terms is often associated with western thinking based on a Eurocentric knowledge system (Aikenhead and Ogawa, 2007) and its attempts to incorporate Indigenous knowledge may be seen as a form of colonialism (Liboiron, 2021). Another point of difference is the view that traditional knowledge is about “ways of knowing, not what is known” and thus does not generate data (footnote 46/p. 53, Liboiron, 2021). Given the distinct nature between traditional ways of knowing and dominant science’s methodologies, the project needs to consider how to implement data principles that are tailored with indigenous rights in mind. One such guideline is the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance (<https://www.gida-global.org/care>): Data principles created to advance the legal principles underlying collective and individual data rights in the context of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP). CARE is distinctly separate from FAIR in that FAIR principles focus on increased data sharing alone, while CARE principles encourage data sharing in both a people-oriented and purpose-oriented way (Global Indigenous Data Alliance, n.d.). Without the consideration of people, data sharing alone creates tension for Indigenous Peoples and ignores power differentials and historical contexts (Global Indigenous Data Alliance, n.d.). The CARE Principles are (Global Indigenous Data Alliance, 2022):

- **Collective Benefit:** Data ecosystems shall be designed and function in ways that enable Indigenous Peoples to derive benefit from the data
- **Authority to Control:** Indigenous Peoples’ rights and interests in Indigenous data must be recognized and their authority to control such data respected
- **Responsibility:** Those working with Indigenous data have a responsibility to share how those data are used to support Indigenous Peoples’ self-determination and collective benefit
- **Ethics:** Indigenous Peoples’ rights and wellbeing should be the primary concern at all stages of the data life cycle and across the data ecosystem

Regarding the last principle of ethics, as per the ICEBERG DoA Section 4 Ethics Self-Assessment, the project will follow the ethical and methodological guidelines of the International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA, 2020), and in Greenland also the Inuit Circumpolar Council’s (ICC) protocols on Ethical and Equitable Engagement (ICC, 2022). These principles include:

- Responding to and supporting local communities’ needs with the research and knowledge co-produced
- Respecting and including Indigenous ways of knowing
- Respecting free prior informed consent (FPIC), a principle that has been endorsed by the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples

Stakeholder engagement will follow the recommendations of:

- Integrated European Polar Research Programme (EU-PolarNet 2020)
- EU-PolarNet White paper on stakeholder engagement in polar research (Latola et al., 2020)
- A toolkit for Community Based Participatory Research in Greenland (Rink and Reimer, 2019)
- Facilitating increased engagement between the research communities of Greenland and the U.S. (key learnings here apply generally, not just to American researchers) (Culler et al., 2018)

The recommendations of the above resources highlight the importance of adopting a high degree of coordination among different activities to avoid stakeholders’ “research fatigue” while optimising efforts. Other recommendations include trust building and early engagement, joint definition of research

questions, proper allocation of time and funding, diversity and equity in the engagement process, seeking for participation rather than collaboration, and careful and coordinated identification of stakeholder contact points (i.e. intermediaries). Building on these existing guidelines and protocols, ICEBERG will co-develop and implement an ethics evaluation framework, which will be presented in D6.3 Ethics Management Plan. In addition, the ICEBERG Code of Conduct (D4.2) is a framework for self-regulation that includes practices for research collaboration with Indigenous communities.

8.2 Artificial Intelligence and machine learning

The ICEBERG project involves machine learning and AI in several methodologies. Consortium partner SCI has created the Coastal Marine Litter Observatory (CMLO), which uses unmanned aerial systems and machine learning algorithms to automatically detect and map marine litter in coastal zones. Time-lapse cameras installed by CAU will also use machine learning approaches to analyse time-series data. For modelling results with pathways and impact of pollutants in seawater, GEOMAR may use AI for analyses of model results and for coding scripts for analysing model results.

As a quality assurance for AI data, human oversight is required for data validation and monitoring. For AI activities used for detecting litter on collected drone images, developers and deployers are involved in the process of training, monitoring and validating AI therefore maintaining human agency and oversight requirements. End-users and the public can be informed about the employed AI methods in the CMLO platform website (<https://cmlo.aegean.gr/>). SCI will self-assess the trustworthiness of their AI by undertaking the Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI). Confidence level on AI decisions are also provided. For the time-lapse images and time-series datasets, these will be analysed by machine learning approaches but there will still be human oversight to help ensure that the results derived from the data are accurate. Humans (including local community members) perform quality checks on the cameras to ensure that the time-series data used for analysis is of high quality, accurate, and reliable.

To ensure data protection regarding drone images, a quality check will be done to detect images that unintentionally capture people in it. AI does not collect, maintain or process personal data. However, it may happen to unintentionally capture people in images during flight missions. SCI will take actions for maintaining anonymity by blurring/deleting such parts. Time-lapse data will be stored and processed according to the principles of the EASA Privacy Handbook of Drone Rules for Recreational Users (https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/privacyhandbook_en.pdf). CAU is supported by CAU Research Data Management to ensure data protection, fairness, and non-discrimination (<https://www.datamanagement.uni-kiel.de/en>).

The following guidelines for data collection and handling will be followed:

- Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
- Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence
- Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)
- ESA (European Space Agency) Corporate Social Responsibility Code of Conduct
- EASA Privacy Handbook of Drone Rules for Recreational Users
- EU Commission - Ethics for researchers

Potential negative social and/or environmental impacts (e.g., decision making, profiling, surveillance) and how they will be minimized will be discussed in the Ethics Management Plan (D6.3).

8.3 Living and non-living samples

ICEBERG project researchers will strive to collect living and non-living samples from the local environment and ecosystems in a low-impact way to avoid potential risks. Standard methodologies will

be used to collect samples. Biological material transfer documents may be required for transporting of samples between countries.

The work on in vitro human cells will be performed in WP2 using commercially available human cell lines. Cell derivatives will be stored until maximum two years after the end of the project, after which they will be discarded. All information is property of the provider (HPACC or Biopredic) and non-disclosed to the owner, with exception of the information that is publicly disclosed by means of websites (<https://www.culturecollections.org.uk/>, <https://www.biopredic.com/>).

The following guidelines will be followed for data collection and handling:

- DFG Guide to Good Scientific Practice
- Nagoya Protocol
- Research in Svalbard (RiS) guidelines

Potential risks to the local environment and ecosystems and how to mitigate these risks will be discussed in the Ethics Management Plan (D6.3).

9 References

- Aikenhead, G. S., & Ogawa, M. (2007). Indigenous knowledge and science revisited. *Cultural Studies of Science Education*, 2, 539-620.
- Brodkorb, A., Egger, L., Alminger, M., Alvito, P., Assunção, R., Ballance, S., ... & Recio, I. (2019). INFOGEST static in vitro simulation of gastrointestinal food digestion. *Nature protocols*, 14(4), 991-1014.
- Culler, L., Lund, S., Nymand, J., and Virginia, R. (2018). Facilitating increased engagement between the research communities of Greenland and the U.S.
<https://sites.google.com/dartmouth.edu/nuukworkshop/workshop-report-pdf>
- EU-PolarNet. (2020). Integrated European Polar Research Programme. <https://eu-polarnet.eu/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/EPRP.pdf>
- Global Indigenous Data Alliance. n.d. CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance
<https://www.gida-global.org/care>
- Global Indigenous Data Alliance. (2022). Indigenous Data Sovereignty and Governance.
<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5d3799de845604000199cd24/t/640792a43ba5c11a1073bbc8/1678217895508/TheCAREPrinciples.pdf>
- DFG - Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft. (2019). Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice Code of Conduct.
<https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/174052/1a235cb138c77e353789263b8730b1df/kodex-gwp-en-data.pdf>
- Falk-Andersson, J. (2021). Beach litter deep dives—A method for improved understanding of sources of and behaviour behind littering. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 167, 112346.
- Falk-Andersson, J., Tairova, Z., Drægni, T. T., & Haarr, M. L. (2021). Methods for determining the geographical origin and age of beach litter: Challenges and opportunities. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 172, 112901.
- GDPR (2016). General Data Protection Regulation. <https://gdpr-info.eu/>
- IASSA (2020). IASSA Principles and Guidelines for Conducting Ethical Research in the Arctic.
<https://iassa.org/about-iassa/research-principles>
- ICC (2022). Circumpolar Inuit Protocols for Equitable and Ethical Engagement.
<https://www.iarpccollaborations.org/updates/23022>
- Jóźwiak, B., Nawrot, A. (2021). Report on the execution of Sørkapp Marine Litter Cleanup project in 2021. Fundacja forScience. <https://forscience.pl/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/SMLC-Report-2021.pdf>
- Latola, K., Scheepstra, A., Pawlak, J., & Saxinger, G. (2020). White Paper on Status of Stakeholder Engagement in Polar Research. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4255918>

Liboiron, M. (2021). *Pollution is colonialism*. Duke University Press.

Rink, E., & Adler-Reimer, G. (2019). A toolkit for community based participatory research in Greenland.

https://da.uni.gl/media/5467066/greeland_cbpr_toolkit_november2019.pdf

SciDrones PC Spinoff. (n.d.). Data Acquisition Procotol for CMLO.

https://cmlo.aegean.gr/Data_Acquisition_Protocol_v3.pdf

10 Appendix

Appendix Table 1. Questions about data management and ethics answered by all partners.

Questions about data	Explanation
1. What is the purpose of the data you are collecting/generating?	Describe briefly how the data fulfils project objectives.
2. What type of data are you collecting/generating?	Describe briefly what kind of data you are collecting. You may indicate whether the data is quantitative (e.g. marine litter dataset) or qualitative (e.g. interviews).
3. What is the format of the data?	Indicate the expected format of your data (file extension). E.g. interview audio transcripts could be in formats mp3, mp4, wav; while GIS maps could be in formats GeoJSON, tif, kml.
4. What standards apply to the data?	List any standards that the data adheres to. E.g. ISO, metadata standards, standardised vocabularies, standards-based data description to promote findability and interoperability of your datasets. Do not answer "none": If no standards are used, specify how metadata is created/used vocabularies are made available.
5. Does the data collection method follow a standard protocol?	List any standard methodological protocols with citations where possible.
6. Is the data primary or secondary data?	Indicate whether the data is primary (collected by you for the first time and has not undergone analysis or processing yet) or secondary data (whether/how you are reusing existing data, perhaps from another project you worked on).
7. What is the origin of the data?	Indicate where the data was generated or collected e.g. the field work environment if biogeophysical data, or the community name if oral/citizen-sourced data.
8. Who is the data owner?	Data generated is typically owned by the project and your institution. However, you may also need to consider Indigenous knowledge holders' rights to any Indigenous cultural data collected/generated.
9. Where is the data stored during the project?	List all file systems that the data would be stored in throughout the duration of the project. We are particularly interested in whether the data is stored by any third party (e.g. Open Access mapping software).

Questions about data	Explanation
<p>10. If the data is stored/handled by third parties, what is their data protection agreement?</p> <p>11. How long will the data be stored for?</p> <p>12. Are any quality assurance/control methods applied to the data during or post-collection/generation?</p> <p>13. Do you plan to reuse the data generated from the project?</p> <p>13a. Describe any ways that you plan to reuse the data.</p> <p>13b. What is the reuse value of the data to other researchers/third parties?</p>	<p>You may link to the terms and agreement page on their website if available. For example, the interactive community based monitoring platform uses UMAP and their data protection policy can be found on the website.</p> <p>Your institution may have rules regarding data retention and how long data can be stored before termination, particularly personal data.</p> <p>Describe any methods used for QA/QC throughout the entire data collection process. E.g. before: training/competency sessions for community participants, during: QA/QC standards for data collection in your field, after: running diagnostics in data processing software</p> <p>For example, you may wish to compare the project case studies data to other locations you have studied, or future locations you plan to study.</p>
<p>14. Is the data open access?</p> <p>14a. Under which license will data be opened? (recommended: CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International")</p> <p>14b. What additional documentation (e.g., readme files) will be provided to make the data reuse possible?</p> <p>14c. If access to (open) data is restricted, how the access is controlled?</p> <p>14d. If data cannot be Open Access, explain why.</p>	<p>The data is expected to be open access where possible, however there may be restrictions (e.g. proprietary restricted data, data requiring license/special software to access, data that needs to be anonymised for privacy reasons). Note: metadata should always be published even if the data will not be, (preferably) licensed with CC0 "No Rights Reserved".</p>
<p>15. Will you deposit/archive data outputs/metadata in a public repository?</p>	<p>Data should be made available for reuse in accordance with the FAIR principles (if possible).</p>

Questions about data	Explanation
<p>15a. List the repositories you plan to use. E.g. Zenodo, Open Science Framework, any open access repositories specific to your field.</p> <p>15b. Will the planned repositories provide the (meta)data with a persistent identifier (PID) such as DOI or URN?</p> <p>15c. In addition to data, are there any other possible research outputs (e.g., code, software, samples), and how will you make these available for reuse in accordance with the FAIR principles?</p>	
<p>16. Do you plan to collect personal data from participants? If so, what is the protocol and relevant regulation?</p> <p>16a. If yes, who is the data controller?</p> <p>16b. If there is a data processor, who is the data processor?</p> <p>16c. Is there a data processing agreement in place?</p>	<p>Using and handling of personal data must be in compliance with EU directives on privacy protection, as well as country specific regulations. Describe your protocol for protecting participants' personal data (e.g. anonymisation of personal information). Also list any relevant data protection regulations specific to your institution's country (e.g. German Federal Data Protection Act, Hellenic Data Protection Authority, Spanish Data Protection and Digital Rights Act)</p>
<p>17. Does your organisation have a protocol for handling and secure storage of sensitive data?</p>	<p>If this information is not available publicly (e.g. on institution website), you will need to find out from your data protection officer.</p>
<p>18. What are the regulations for data protection for your case study if not under EU directive?</p>	<p>List any relevant regulations here.</p>
<p>19. Does your institution have a data protection officer?</p> <p>19a. If no, who is responsible for data management at your institution?</p>	<p>Provide the contact of your institution's data protection office and/or competent authorities that ensure compliance with rules and standards for data protection.</p>

Questions about data	Explanation
19b. What resources are needed for research data management (RDM) and to make the data FAIR (are there any costs?)?	
20. Does your institution have an ethics committee?	List your institution's ethics committees and/or competent authorities that ensure compliance with rules and standards around research involving people/animals.
21. Do you need to go through an ethics clearance / ethics approval / ethics certificate / statement from an ethics committee?	List the ethics committee steps you need to go through.
22. Which ethical governance procedures are you requested to follow?	List any existing ethical regulations (national laws, institutional guidelines etc.)
23. How do you ensure the voluntariness and the informed consent?	
<p>24. Are you working with vulnerable groups (i.e. Indigenous Peoples, children)?</p> <p>24a. Are there any potential risks for vulnerable groups or cultural heritage resulting from your work?</p> <p>24b. How to mitigate, minimize these risks?</p> <p>24c. How do you ensure sharing data with local communities and Indigenous communities? How do you ensure that data benefit them?</p>	List the vulnerable groups you are working with. Note: cultural heritage might be at risk even in cases when the research doesn't involve human participants (e.g., sacred sites)
25. What ethical guidelines do you follow?	
26. Are there any potential risks to the local environment and ecosystems?	List the potential risks.

Questions about data	Explanation
27. In case of transporting samples between countries, which agreements do you follow?	
28. In case you use AI, how do you ensure human agency, oversight, transparency and accountability?	
29. How do you ensure data protection, fairness, and non-discrimination?	
30. Identify potential negative social and/or environmental impacts (e.g., decision making, profiling, surveillance) and explain how they will be minimized	
31. If you use time-lapse cameras, drones, how do you store and process data in accordance with EU GDPR?	